

Table of Contents

- **Prof. Luiz Bittencourt participated in the Connections to Sustain Science in Latin America Symposium 2025**
- **Five SMARTNESS papers accepted at SBRC 2025!**
- **SMARTNESS participates in the inauguration of ERICSSON's Open Innovation Lab**
- **SMARTNESS Visits Dr. Telêmaco Paioli Melges Sate School in Sumaré-SP**
- **Welcome day at FEEC 2025**
- **Technical visit by Prof. Luiz Bittencourt to the University of Manchester advances Digital Twins research**
- **SMARTNESS celebrates three new MSc defenses**
- **Prof. Christian Rothenberg examines 15 years of Software-Defined Networking (SDN)**
- **New publication at IEEE Network on in-network Quality of Experience**
- **SMARTNESS at CoNEXT 2024**

*Keep up to date with our latest publications, events, news and more!
Follow us on our social media:*

[smartness2030.tech](https://www.facebook.com/smartness2030.tech)

[smartness2030](https://www.linkedin.com/company/smartness2030)

[smartness2030.tech](https://www.instagram.com/smartness2030.tech)

[smartness2030](https://www.youtube.com/channel/smartness2030)

Prof. Luiz Bittencourt Participated in the Connections to Sustain Science in Latin America Symposium 2025

[Read more](#)

Professor Luiz Bittencourt Participates in the Connections to Sustain Science in Latin America Symposium 2025. Professor Luiz Bittencourt presented his research on the Intelligent Computing Continuum, addressing privacy and performance challenges in distributed machine learning. His talk contributed to discussions on optimizing AI-driven systems while ensuring data security. The Connections to Sustain Science in Latin America Symposium 2025, held in Lima, Peru, was organized in partnership with the Universidad de Ingeniería y Tecnología (UTEC). The event brought together scientists, engineers, and medical professionals from Latin America, the Caribbean, the U.S., and Canada to share knowledge, explore scientific advancements, and strengthen regional and international collaborations.

Five SMARTNESS Papers Accepted at SBRC 2025!

[Read more](#)

We are proud to announce that five research papers from our team have been accepted at SBRC 2025! This achievement highlights the dedication and excellence of our researchers in advancing knowledge in networking, AI, cloud computing, and security. Accepted Papers:

- ◆ Stream Ciphers ChaCha, Forró & Xote in Programmable Hardware (Pierini, Teixeira, Rothenberg, Henriques)
- ◆ QoE Analysis of Volumetric Video (Silva, Cesen, Clerici, Rothenberg, Cerqueira, Testoni)
- ◆ DCTPQ: Cloud Gaming Traffic Prioritization (Shirmarz, Marques, Verdi, Singh, Rothenberg)
- ◆ sQGAN for Attack Detection (Abreu, Moura, Rothenberg, Abelém)
- ◆ Drone Deliveries: Collision & Repair Logistics (Feitosa, Barbosa, Bittencourt, Oliveira, R. Junior, Silva)

SMARTNESS participates in the inauguration of ERICSSON's Open Innovation Lab

On February 25, Prof. Christian Rothenberg (Director of SMARTNESS) and Dr. Eduardo Sartori (Technology Transfer Manager of SMARTNESS) attended the inauguration of Ericsson's Open Innovation Lab in Indaiatuba, São Paulo. This new Ericsson laboratory is dedicated to research collaborations in 5G, automation, AI, and virtual reality.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS Visits Dr. Telêmaco Paioli Melges Sate School in Sumaré-SP

On February 25, Dr. Christian Rothenberg (Director of SMARTNESS) and Dr. Eduardo Sartori (Technology Transfer Manager of SMARTNESS) were at the Dr. Telêmaco Paioli Melges State School, in Sumaré-SP, for the first meeting to plan Education and Knowledge Dissemination activities, in partnership with CPTEn - Paulista Center for Energy Training Studies. They were accompanied by Dr. Danusia Ferreira, associate researcher at CPTEn, and received by the Director of the School, Prof. Mario Ferreira Sarraipa, and his team.

[Read more](#)

Welcome day at FEEC 2025

[Read more](#)

The School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (FEEC/UNICAMP) held its annual “Encontro FEEC” on February 22, offering new students and the general public a high-level view of ongoing research. SMARTNESS researchers from LCA presented their latest research findings. While AdRoLab, led by Prof. Eric Rhomer, showcased robotics in smart homes using various robots, the INTRIG research group, led by Prof. Christian Rothenberg, presented work on route planning with drones and holograms, with focus on future 5G and 6G applications. The event encouraged collaboration and innovation.

Technical visit by Prof. Luiz Bittencourt to the University of Manchester advances Digital Twins research

[Read more](#)

On a technical visit to the UK between Feb 12th and 24th, Prof. Luiz Bittencourt (Unicamp/Smartness2030 Researcher) participated in discussions at the University of Manchester to strengthen international collaborations and advanced research on Digital Twins as part of the FAPESP-SPRINT project. The visit focused on exploring innovative computational models to enhance the scalability and efficiency of cyber-physical systems in real-world applications.

SMARTNESS celebrates three new MSc defenses

SMARTNESS announces three new MSc defenses, showcasing research on optimizing cloud-native communications, industrial networking, and security in programmable data planes. Arthur Simas introduces eZtunnel, an eBPF-based solution that reduces packet processing overhead in cloud-native environments. Sergio Rossi investigates the integration of TSN and 5G to enable deterministic, low-latency communication for smart industries. Rodrigo Pierini develops a compliance verification framework leveraging programmable networks to improve security in data centers. These defenses reinforce SMARTNESS ERC's contributions to advanced networking research.

[Read more](#)

Prof. Christian Rothenberg examines 15 Years of Software-Defined Networking (SDN)

Prof. Dr. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP), Coordinator of SMARTNESS 2030, presented the lecture titled "15 Years of Software-Defined Networking (SDN): Quo Vadis, SDN?" at the II Open Networks Training Workshop in Brasília. The talk revisited SDN's foundational principles, showcasing its transformative impact on network agility, automation, and cost efficiency while addressing critical challenges such as interoperability and scalability. It also explored cutting-edge advancements, including Intent-Based Networking (IBN), AI/ML-driven network optimization, and programmable testbeds for advanced research, highlighting SDN's pivotal role in shaping the future of open and disaggregated network technologies.

[Read more](#)

New publication at IEEE Network on in-network Quality of Experience

Video Streaming QoE Meets Programmable Data Planes: The Case of In-Network QoE for 360° VR

Francisco Germano Vogt*, Fabricio Eduardo Rodriguez Cesen¹, Ariel Góes de Castro², Sumeet Kumar Singh³, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli⁴, Christian Esteve Rothenberg⁵, and Gianni Antichi^{6*}

Abstract—Recent advancements in video streaming technologies have brought about a new era of user experiences, including gaming and online events. However, ensuring a good user experience remains a significant challenge. The pursuit of self-driving networks has increased the demand for intelligent, edge-based networking solutions. Delivering high-quality video streaming experiences faces hurdles such as varying network conditions, device diversity, and content complexity, along with the inter-twined adaptivity of over-the-top services and modern network management systems. In this work, we elaborate on video streaming quality of experience (QoE) improvements based on recent advances in programmable networks. We explore the concept of in-network QoE (INQoE) by discussing benefits, challenges, and opportunities. Furthermore, we present a pure data plane strategy to estimate and improve the QoE of 360-degree virtual reality video streaming. Our results show an INQoE management strategy can effectively keep the QoE close to optimal (4.8 on a scale of 5) under a congestion scenario. Finally, we conclude with a roadmap of research challenges and opportunities around INQoE.

Index Terms—Quality of Experience, Next-Generation Networks, Artificial Intelligence, Software-defined Networks, Video Streaming, INQoE.

I. INTRODUCTION

IEEE scholix of ieee.computer. (2025) mobile networks.

these applications demand, such as minimal latency and large bandwidth. Exemplifying this, recent work [1] has shown that an increase of 5 ms in latency can degrade QoE from 8 to 36 percent in virtual reality (VR) video streaming applications.

To meet the demands of these applications and deliver a satisfying QoE for users, the network should make timely decisions and adjust network policies in response to the root causes of QoE degradation. To this end, it is fundamental to rely on efficient monitoring capabilities. Recent research efforts [2], [3] have focused on monitoring user QoE and applying different network policies to improve it if necessary. However, despite their accuracy in estimating and predicting user QoE, strategies based on QoE inference in the user's player or control plane are often insufficient for the next generation of video streaming applications. To change some network policy, for example, in the event of a problem, these strategies need to communicate with the data plane, taking around up to tens of milliseconds [4], which is beyond the latency requirements of some applications [5].

With the recent advent of network programmability, efforts have been devoted to moving QoE inference and optimization from the control plane to the data plane [6], [7]. For

Researchers led by SMARTNESS propose a novel strategy to improve Quality of Experience (QoE) in 360° VR streaming within the network using P4 programmable data planes, to address critical challenges in adaptive video delivery. The work highlights the effectiveness of in-network QoE (INQoE) solutions to improve the video QoE score, even in congested scenarios. This research demonstrates how integrating QoE management into network infrastructure can ensure high-quality streaming while supporting next-generation applications like VR gaming and live events.

[Read more](#)

SMARTNESS at CoNEXT 2024

[Read more](#)

The SMARTNESS team actively contributed to ACM CoNEXT 2024 in Los Angeles, presenting cutting-edge research. Francisco Vogt and Prof. Dr. Marcelo Luizelli introduced InReal, optimizing in-network resource scaling for VNFs, and proposed a novel telemetry approach leveraging programmable switches. Washington Silva demonstrated an AR inference method for edge computing, reducing latency. Guilherme Matos explored functional decomposition of monolithic applications, improving cache efficiency. These contributions advance networking, computing, and edge intelligence.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS & DISCLAIMER

This work has been performed within the framework of the FAPESP Engineering Research Center (ERC) Program under FAPESP grant agreement #2021/00199-8 (SMARTNESS).

The information in this document reflects the SMARTNESS ERC's view, but the partner institutions of SMARTNESS are not liable for any use that may be made of any of the information contained therein. The views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily represent those of FAPESP or the other granting authorities. Neither FAPESP nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The views expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent Ericsson's official standpoint.

Keep up to date with our latest publications, events, news and more!

Follow us on our social media:

[smartness2030.tech](https://www.facebook.com/smartness2030.tech)

[smartness2030](https://www.linkedin.com/company/smartness2030)

[smartness2030.tech](https://www.instagram.com/smartness2030.tech)

[smartness2030](https://www.youtube.com/channel/smartness2030)